

1 **Hyaluronan exerts unique microbiome and metabolic effects compared with pectin: a**
2 **multi-omics study of dietary polysaccharides**

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15 **ABSTRACT**

16 Dietary polysaccharides are increasingly recognized as modulators of host metabolism through
17 intestinal interactions, yet not all exert comparable systemic effects. In this context, dietary hyaluronan
18 (HA) is distinguished by its clinical efficacy on connective tissues. We investigated whether oral HA
19 modulates the small-intestinal microbiome, systemic metabolome, and lipid metabolism, and compared
20 its effects with pectin. Using a healthy murine model, we combined 16S rRNA sequencing,
21 metabolomics, lipidomics, and correlation analyses. Oral HA triggered profound and previously
22 undescribed shifts in the small-intestinal microbiome, while pectin's effects were markedly weaker.
23 Both supplements increased microbial diversity, with HA specifically enriching taxa such as
24 *Turicibacter*, *Clostridium*, and *Lachnoclostridium*. HA was also associated with elevated systemic
25 metabolites, enhancing redox status. Hydroxybutyrate and related metabolites increased, consistent
26 with enhanced lipolysis. HA was linked to reduced glycogen degradation without effects on synthesis,
27 whereas pectin was related to lowered glycogen synthesis without alterations in degradation. Notably,
28 only HA was associated with modulated plasma and hepatic lipid metabolism. Specifically, lipid
29 mediators playing roles in organismal homeostasis, inflammation, and pain modulation were altered.
30 Collectively, these findings indicate that oral HA exerts a unique effect on the intestinal microbiome,
31 systemic metabolome, and lipidome compared to pectin.

33 **Abbreviations**

34 AMOVA - analysis of molecular variance, ALT – aminotransferase, FA 20:4 – arachidonic acid, FA
35 20:5 - eicosapentaenoic acid, FA 22:4 – docosatetraenoic acid, FA 22:6 – docosahexaenoic acid, FA -
36 fatty acid, GABA - gamma-aminobutyric acid, GIT - gastrointestinal tract, HA - hyaluronic acid ,
37 HOMOVA - homogeneity of molecular variance, IMP - Inosine monophosphate, LC-MS - liquid
38 chromatography–mass spectrometry, LPC – lysophosphatidylcholine, LPCAT -
39 lysophosphatidylcholine acyltransferase, LPE – lysophosphatidylethanolamines, MBOAT -
40 membrane-bound O-acyltransferase domain enzyme, MDA – malondialdehyde, NAD⁺, NADH -
41 nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide, PC – phosphatidylcholine, PC-O - ether-linked
42 phosphatidylcholine, PE – phosphatidylethanolamines, PE-O - ether-linked
43 phosphatidylethanolamines , PICRUS - Phylogenetic Investigation of Communities by
44 Reconstruction of Unobserved States, *p.o.* - orally administered, SCFA - short chain fatty acid, TCA -
45 tricarboxylic acid cycle (Krebs cycle), TG – triglyceride, UDP-Glc - Uridine 5'-diphosphate-glucose,
46 UDP Glc-NAc – Uridine-diphosphate-N-acetylglucosamine

47

1 INTRODUCTION

Orally administered hyaluronan (*p.o.* HA) has been reported to exert beneficial effects across multiple clinical contexts, including joint function, inflammatory status, skin aging, and metabolic health [1,2]. However, these outcomes remain mechanistically paradoxical, as high-molecular-weight HA exhibits negligible systemic absorption after oral intake [3]. Thus, the mechanisms by which *p.o.* HA elicits extra-intestinal metabolic effects remain unclear. Early studies proposed direct immunomodulatory signalling through innate immune receptors such as TLR2 and TLR4 [4], but these findings were mainly based on *in vitro* systems using artificially fragmented HA, which do not reflect the physicochemical properties or exposure route of orally administered high-molecular-weight HA. Consequently, direct receptor-mediated signalling is unlikely to be the dominant mechanism *in vivo*.

Instead, increasing evidence supports an indirect mechanism mediated by intestinal microbial and metabolic processes. Like other dietary polysaccharides, HA undergoes gastrointestinal degradation, primarily through microbial enzymatic activity [3,5]. Several intestinal bacteria express hyaluronate lyases that cleave HA into unsaturated oligosaccharides [6,7]. In mice, *p.o.* HA is progressively depolymerized along the gut: intermediate fragments (~50–600 kDa) occur in the small intestine (SI), while unsaturated oligosaccharides accumulate predominantly in the colon but are also present in the SI [3]. Despite minimal systemic absorption ($\leq 0.2\%$) and rapid clearance from the bloodstream [3,8], HA supplementation consistently alters plasma metabolic profiles, including markers of lipid catabolism [9], supporting the intestine as the primary site mediating *p.o.* HA effects. Similar microbiome- and metabolome-modulating effects have been described for other fermentable polysaccharides such as pectin [10,11], suggesting that some reported benefits of *p.o.* HA may overlap with general fiber-driven mechanisms. Nevertheless, *p.o.* HA stands out among other polysaccharides due to its clinical efficacy in connective tissues [9]. Distinguishing HA-specific effects from broader polysaccharide responses, therefore, requires direct comparative studies.

Most research on dietary polysaccharides has focused on the cecum and colon, where microbial density is highest, and fermentation products accumulate [12,13]. This emphasis overlooks the SI, where polysaccharides are first encountered, partially degraded, and converted into bioactive intermediates influencing host physiology before reaching the colon. The SI possesses specialized epithelial and immune structures that sense luminal metabolites, and hosts a dynamic, diet-responsive microbiome enriched in taxa implicated in barrier function, immune modulation, and energy metabolism [14,15]. These characteristics position the SI microbiome as a plausible yet underexplored mediator of polysaccharide-induced metabolic effects. Beyond direct substrate utilization, polysaccharide effects often emerge from cooperative microbial degradation and metabolic cross-feeding [16–18]. Such interactions can reorganize community structure and generate metabolites that influence host energy metabolism and barrier integrity [12,19]. While these mechanisms are well documented in the colon, their relevance in the SI is poorly defined. It remains unclear how structurally

84 distinct polysaccharides, such as HA and pectin, differentially influence the SI microbial ecosystem and
85 whether the resulting microbial metabolites contribute to systemic metabolic outcomes. Pectin, a well-
86 characterized and widely used fermentable anionic polysaccharide with established effects on gut
87 microbiota and host metabolism [20], was therefore selected as a reference to distinguish HA-specific
88 effects from general polysaccharide-mediated responses.

89 We hypothesized that *p.o.* HA modulates host metabolism primarily through alterations in the SI
90 microbiome and its metabolic outputs, in a manner distinct from other fermentable polysaccharides. To
91 test this, we investigated the impact of *p.o.* HA on the SI microbiome of healthy mice and its associated
92 metabolic consequences using integrated metabolomic and lipidomic analyses. By directly comparing
93 HA with pectin, we aimed to distinguish HA-specific effects from shared polysaccharide-driven
94 mechanisms, with particular emphasis on SI processes and systemic lipid metabolism.

95

96 **2 MATERIALS AND METHODS**

97 **2.1 HA or pectin supplementation of healthy mice (14 days)**

98 Female C57BL/6 mice from the IBP CAS colony were used (30 animals in total). After weaning
99 (~4 weeks of age), the mice were cohoused for 2 weeks on a standard autoclaved diet to normalize and
100 maximally unify their microbiota across different individuals. Mice (18-20 g in weight) were then
101 randomly distributed into cages of 5 animals, with two cages (10 females) assigned to each experimental
102 group. Animals were weighed and marked with ear tags. Experimental groups were as follows: HA (2.5
103 mg ml⁻¹) N = 10, pectin (low degree of esterification; Sigma, cat. number 93854, apple pectin, ethylene
104 oxide-sterilized powder, 2.5 mg ml⁻¹), N = 10; and control (drinking water from the animal facility), N
105 = 10. The M_w distribution of HA (M_w 1.7 MDa, M_w/M_n 1.491) and pectin (M_w 0.25 MDa, M_w/M_n 3.289)
106 were determined by a combination of size-exclusion chromatography with multi-angle light scattering
107 (Figure S14) as described previously [21]. The pectin with a degree of esterification 67 % were
108 characterized by ¹H NMR at 700 MHz, and the molar ratio of methylester/acetate/rhamnose was
109 determined 19/1.4/1 (Figure S15). Pectin monosaccharide composition is described in detail [22].

110 The supplements were administered as a sterile solution in drinking water for 14 days, which was
111 changed every other day. Mice had ad libitum access to food (maintenance diet for rats and mice,
112 Altromin International, cat. n. 1320, sterilized at 120 °C for 45 minutes) and water during the entire
113 experimental period. The amount of consumed drinking water with the supplement per cage was
114 monitored daily by weighing on lab scales. After 14 days, the mice were anesthetized by isoflurane
115 inhalation, and the stomach and SI were collected under sterile conditions. Plasma was separated by
116 centrifugation (350 g/10 min, RT). Organs, tissue, and the contents of the stomach, SI, cecum, and colon
117 were immediately frozen in liquid nitrogen and stored at -80 °C until analysis. All procedures were
118 approved by the Animal Care Committee of the Czech Academy of Sciences (protocol no. 129/2023)
119 and conducted in accordance with the EU guidelines and the NIH Guide for the Care and Use of
120 Laboratory Animals. The Institute of Biophysics is authorized to use experimental animals (file no.
121 16OZ22300/2019-18,134; ID: 43049/2020-MZE-18134).

122 **2.2. Isolation and amplification of DNA, analysis of sequencing data**

123 Sample collection: Gastric or SI contents were expelled into sterile Eppendorf tubes under laminar
124 flow conditions. The stomach was opened, and the digesta was carefully squeezed out. The whole SI
125 was cut into several pieces, and luminal content was expelled by gentle manual extrusion. Gastric and
126 SI contents were frozen immediately at -80 °C. Gastric or intestinal tissues were gently shaken in 1 mL
127 sterile PBS for 5 min. The PBS was centrifuged (8000g, 30 min, 4 °C), and the pellet was stored at -80
128 °C.

129 DNA isolation, amplification, and sequence analysis: DNA from stomach and SI contents was
130 extracted using the PureLink Microbiome DNA Purification Kit (Invitrogen) according to the

131 manufacturer's instructions. DNA concentration was measured with a Nanodrop ND-1000
132 spectrophotometer (Thermo Fisher Scientific), and quality was assessed by electrophoresis on a 1%
133 agarose gel. The V3–V4 region of the 16S rRNA gene was amplified using a two-step PCR protocol
134 and sequenced on an Illumina MiSeq platform (2 × 300 bp paired-end reads; service: INVUEW
135 Microbiome profiling 3.0, Eurofins Genomics). Data processing followed the standard MiSeq Mothur
136 pipeline: paired reads were assembled into contigs and quality-filtered; unique sequences were
137 identified and pre-clustered to reduce sequencing errors; chimeras were removed. Taxonomic
138 classification was performed using the SILVA reference database. Sequences were clustered into OTUs
139 (Operational Taxonomic Units) at 97% similarity (cutoff 0.03) [23].

140 **2.3. Metabolomic analysis**

141 Samples of tissue homogenates, plasma, and contents of the gastrointestinal tract were extracted
142 with chilled (-80 °C) methanol (1:4, v/v), dried under a stream of nitrogen and dissolved in 100 µl of
143 0.1% formic acid or 60% isopropanol (v/v) for analysis by means of reversed-phase chromatography
144 (RPLC) or hydrophilic interaction chromatography (HILIC), respectively. A Vanquish Horizon
145 UHPLC system coupled with an Exploris 240 mass spectrometer (Thermo Fisher Scientific) equipped
146 with an electrospray ionization source was used. RPLC was performed according to [24] on an Acquity
147 C18 column UPLC HSS T3 (2.1×100 mm, 1.8 µm) (Waters) with a gradient elution of 0.1% formic
148 acid in water (v/v) and 0.1% formic acid in 95% acetonitrile/5% water (v/v). Basic HILIC was
149 performed according to [25] on an Acquity BEH Amide column (2.1×100 mm, 1.7 µm) (Waters) with
150 a gradient elution of ammonium acetate (10 mmol l⁻¹), ammonium hydroxide (10 mmol l⁻¹) in 5%
151 acetonitrile (v/v, pH 9.0), and 95% acetonitrile (v/v). Metabolites were detected in negative ion mode,
152 utilizing an ion transfer tube temperature of 350 °C, a sheath gas pressure of 60 psi, an auxiliary gas
153 flow of 20, and a spray voltage of 3.5 kV or -2.5 kV. MS data (*m/z* 70-800) were collected using a
154 dynamic exclusion list and a targeted inclusion list updated in the AcquireX data acquisition mode to
155 achieve optimal metabolite identification in Compound Discoverer 3.3 software (Thermo Fisher
156 Scientific, Waltham, USA). Data were further processed in MetaboAnalyst [26].

157 **2.4. Lipidomic analysis**

158 Lipids from plasma were mixed with cooled isopropanol containing a mixture of internal standards
159 (Avanti EquiSPLASH, 330731; C16:0 L-carnitine-d9, 870323P; cholesterol-d7, 700041P; Arachidonic
160 acid-d11, 861810E). The microtubes were vortexed (2000 rpm, 2 minutes) and stored in the freezer (-
161 20 °C) overnight for complete protein precipitation. The solutions were centrifuged and transferred to
162 vials, and LC-MS analysis was performed. A pooled sample solution was prepared by mixing aliquots
163 of each sample, using the same procedure as for the standard samples.

164 Liver samples were prepared according to the Bligh & Dyer HCl protocol [27]. 80 µl of liver
165 homogenates (100 mg ml⁻¹) were mixed with 10 µl of 10x diluted Mouse SPLASH Lipidomix (330707),

166 800 µl of 0.1 M HCl:MeOH was added and vortexed for 10 minutes, 400 µl chloroform was pipetted,
167 and the tube was vortexed for 10 minutes again. The samples were stored overnight in the freezer to
168 enhance protein precipitation. Samples were centrifuged the next day. The lower layer was collected
169 and evaporated under steam of N₂. The extracts were redissolved in 80% IPA+1% Formic acid.

170 Plasma was analysed using an in-house untargeted lipidomics method using RP-UHPLC-MS with
171 DDA in positive and negative modes on Orbitrap Exploris 240 [9]. Every sample was injected twice.
172 Blank and pooled samples were injected after every ten sample injections. The order of injected samples
173 was set randomly.

174 Liver samples were analysed using untargeted in-house HILIC method using Accucore HILIC
175 (2.1x150 mm, 2.6 µm), A: 10 mM CH₃COONH₄ in 30% ACN (pH=4, adjusted by CH₃COOH) B: 10
176 mM CH₃COONH₄ in 95% ACN (pH = 4, adjusted by CH₃COOH – same volume of CH₃COOH as in
177 MP A) gradient elution (0-5 min, 60 % B, 5-10 min 60-20 % B; 10-11 min 20% B; 11-11.1 min 20-
178 100 % B; 11.1-14 min – 100 % B). Column and autosampler temperatures were set to 50 °C and 6 °C,
179 respectively. Injection volume was 3 µl. The flow rate was 0.4 mL/min. The positive and negative
180 modes were run separately. MS parameters were as follows: Positive capillary voltage 3500 V, Negative
181 capillary voltage 2000 V, Sheath gas 35 arb, Auxiliary gas 10 arb, Sweep gas 0 arb, Ion Transfer Tube
182 temperature 300 °C, Vaporizer temperature 350 °C, RF Lens 75 %, Full MS resolution 45 000, Full MS
183 range 200-1700 m/z, ddMS resolution 11250, Window width 1.5 Da. A targeted inclusion list for pre-
184 selected lipids was used to prioritize their annotation. The blank and pooled samples were injected after
185 every ten sample injections. The order of injected samples was set randomly.

186 The data were processed using Compound Discoverer 3.3, and peaks were manually inspected.
187 Wrongly integrated peaks were fixed using Tracefinder. The unique peak areas were processed in Excel
188 to achieve fold changes for each lipid.

189 **2.5. Aminotransferase activity assay kit**

190 The aminotransferase (ALT) activity was measured in the plasma of healthy mice with HA or
191 pectin supplementation for 14 days. The enzyme activity was measured using the ALT Kit (10452)
192 according to the manufacturer's instructions. Standard for calibration was Biocal C00.003.

193 **2.6. Functional prediction of microbial communities**

194 The functional potential of the SI microbiota was inferred using PICRUST2 (Phylogenetic
195 Investigation of Communities by Reconstruction of Unobserved States, version 2). This bioinformatics
196 approach predicts the genomic content of microbial communities from 16S rRNA gene profiles (here
197 based on the V3–V4 hypervariable regions). Briefly, representative OTU sequences were
198 phylogenetically placed into a reference tree of sequenced genomes, and evolutionary relatedness was
199 then used to estimate the likely gene content of each OTU. Predicted gene families were assigned as

200 Enzyme Commission (EC) numbers, which were subsequently mapped to MetaCyc metabolic pathways
201 using the MinPath algorithm. The accuracy of these predictions is expressed by the Nearest Sequenced
202 Taxon Index (NSTI), which quantifies the average phylogenetic distance between observed OTUs and
203 their closest sequenced reference genome. In this dataset, the mean NSTI was 0.17 (median 0.12), which
204 corresponds to the boundary between moderate and good predictive reliability for murine microbiome
205 datasets, where somewhat higher NSTI values are expected due to fewer sequenced reference genomes
206 compared to human-associated taxa. Consistently, the observed distribution indicates that most OTUs
207 were closely related to sequenced genomes, with only a few more distant outliers.

208 **2.7. Correlation between microbiome and metabolome, lipidome data**

209 For the correlation analysis, log₂-transformed metabolomic and lipidomic data, as well as the
210 relative abundances of bacterial taxa that exhibited statistically significant differences between
211 experimental groups, were used. Associations between metabolite and lipidomic levels with bacterial
212 abundances were evaluated using Spearman's rank correlation. Correlation matrices were performed
213 and visualized in R Studio.

214 **2.8. Statistical analysis**

215 Diversity analysis: Alpha diversity was estimated using the inverse Simpson index [23,28].
216 Differences between groups were evaluated using the Kruskal-Wallis test followed by Dunn's post hoc
217 test with Benjamini-Hochberg correction. Beta diversity was analysed using analysis of molecular
218 variance (AMOVA) and homogeneity of molecular variance (HOMOVA) [28]. Due to high
219 computational demands, parts of the analysis were performed using the Masaryk University
220 Metacentrum computing grid (Brno, Czechia). Visualization was done with MEGAN6, STAMP, and
221 R. PCA plots were generated in STAMP from OTU classifications. Bar plots were produced at both the
222 phylum and genus levels. The statistical differences in the selected microbial data (Fig. 1D, Relative
223 abundance of selected genera) were tested for normality using the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test; as the
224 data were normally distributed, an ANOVA with a Tukey post-hoc test was performed. No
225 normalization was performed in the tool; the Mus Musculus (KEGG) pathway library was used.

226 The lipidomic and metabolomic data were presented as the median \pm SD. Normalization of
227 lipidomic data was performed on the total area ratio of lipid/IS. The fold changes were calculated by
228 dividing the normalized area ratio of each injection by the average of all samples. The statistical
229 evaluation of lipidomic data was performed by the Mann-Whitney non-parametric test. In
230 metabolomics, fold changes were calculated as peak areas divided by the average of all samples.
231 MetaboAnalyst [26] was used for PCA and PLSDA analysis in both lipidomics and metabolomics, as
232 well as pathway analysis in MetaboAnalyst. For the metabolome data, ANOVA with Fisher's Least
233 Significant Difference post hoc test was used. To perform Pathway analysis for metabolomics, fold

234 change values were uploaded to MetaboAnalyst. R Studio was used for lipidomic Volcano plots with
235 values calculated using the Mann-Whitney test, and BIOPAN [29] was used for statistical analysis.

236 3. RESULTS

237 **3.1 Oral administration of HA alters the composition of the small intestinal microbiota** 238 **compared with pectin**

239 The microbiota of the SI and stomach of healthy mice was analysed following *p.o.* HA or pectin
240 administration using 16S rRNA gene sequencing. PCA of the SI microbiota revealed clustering of
241 samples according to supplementation group (control, HA, and pectin), indicating that both
242 polysaccharides altered microbial community composition relative to water controls (Figure 1A).
243 Notably, samples from HA-supplemented mice formed a distinct and compact cluster, whereas
244 communities from the pectin and water groups showed greater dispersion. These observations were
245 supported by AMOVA analysis based on beta diversity, which demonstrated significant differences
246 among all groups (HA-water, HA-pectin, and pectin-water; all $p < 0.001^*$) with the most pronounced
247 separation observed for the HA group. HOMOVA analysis further revealed significantly lower within-
248 group variability in the HA group compared with both water and pectin groups (HA-water, $p < 0.001^*$;
249 HA-pectin $p < 0.001^*$), whereas no significant difference in dispersion was observed between the pectin
250 and water groups (pectin-water; $p = 0.209$). Together, these analyses indicate that HA supplementation
251 induces a more uniform restructuring of the SI microbiota than pectin (Figure 1A). Alpha diversity
252 analysis showed a significant increase in microbial richness in the SI in both the HA and pectin groups
253 compared to the water control group, indicating a polymer-associated redistribution of microbial taxa
254 (Figure 1B). In contrast, no statistically significant changes in microbial diversity or composition were
255 detected in the gastric microbiota following supplementation with either HA or pectin (beta diversity
256 Figure S1A, alpha diversity Figure S1B, taxonomic distribution at the genus level Figure S1C).

257 Genus-level analysis revealed marked differences in the SI microbiota between control and
258 polysaccharide-supplemented groups (Figure 1C). In the water control group, the genus *Lactobacillus*
259 (currently split into *Lactobacillus*, *Ligilactobacillus*, and *Limosilactobacillus*) [30] dominated the
260 community, accounting for ~75% of total sequences. HA supplementation led to a significant reduction
261 in the abundance of these taxa to ~32%, while the decrease observed with pectin (~40%) did not reach
262 statistical significance (Figure S2A). The relative abundance of *Muribaculum* was significantly reduced
263 in the HA supplementation group but not in the pectin group compared with controls (Figure S2A).
264 Both HA and pectin supplementation were associated with increased relative abundance of
265 *Colidextribacter* and *Bifidobacterium*. In contrast, a significant increase in *Bacteroides* was observed
266 exclusively in the HA-supplemented group compared with the water control. Several additional genera,
267 including *Intestinimonas*, *Lachnoclostridium*, and *Turicibacter*, showed increased relative abundance
268 following supplementation with both polymers, with significantly higher levels in the HA group than
269 in the pectin group (Figure 1C, D).

270

271 **Figure 1. Effect of per oral HA or pectin supplementation on the small intestine microbiota of healthy**
 272 **C57BL/6 mice.** A) PCA of the small intestine (SI) microbiota. PCA plot generated from the distribution of
 273 individual OTUs across all samples using STAMP software. B) Alpha diversity of the SI microbiota. The samples
 274 were calculated using the inverse Simpson index. C) Relative taxonomic distribution at the genus level of the SI.
 275 D) Relative abundance of selected genera of the SI with their potential biological functions, * treatment vs Ctrl #
 276 HA vs pectin. E, F) PICRUSt analysis predicted the functional potential of the microbial community in the SI. All
 277 reported outputs of comparing the HA (red) vs. control (blue) (water) or HA (red) vs. pectin (green) are statistically
 278 significant. $N = 10$.

279 To assess the predicted functional potential of the SI microbial communities, metagenomic
 280 inference was performed using PICRUSt2. This analysis suggested an increased relative abundance of
 281 predicted pathways associated with carbohydrate metabolism, including the non-oxidative pentose
 282 phosphate pathway and pathways related to glycogen and starch biosynthesis, in the HA group
 283 compared with both control and pectin groups (Figure 1E, F). Similar trends were also observed after
 284 pectin supplementation, although the effects were less pronounced (Figure 1F, Figure S2B).

285 3.2. HA and pectin supplementation differentially modulate the metabolome

286 Untargeted metabolomic profiling of liver tissue, plasma, and SI, cecal, and colonic contents was
 287 performed using RPLC and HILIC. The analysis revealed that both HA and pectin supplementation
 288 exerted the most pronounced effects on the liver metabolome, whereas effects in plasma and SI were
 289 weaker, and only minor changes were observed in cecal and colonic contents (Figure 2A; Figure S3).
 290 HA-treated samples formed a tight and distinct cluster mainly in the liver, but also in the SI, while
 291 pectin- and water-treated samples displayed greater dispersion (Figure 2A). Based on these

292 observations, subsequent analyses focused primarily on hepatic metabolomic alterations. Liver integrity
293 was confirmed by ALT measurements, which showed unchanged ALT concentrations, suggesting no
294 evidence of hepatic overload following HA or pectin supplementation in healthy female C57BL/6 mice
295 (Figure S4).

296 Statistically significant metabolites were identified by ANOVA ($p < 0.05$) and confirmed by
297 library matching. HA supplementation induced a distinct shift in hepatic energy metabolism (Figure
298 2B, C). Notably, only HA supplementation significantly increased hydroxybutyrate levels, a marker of
299 enhanced lipolysis, while reducing the inosine monophosphate (IMP). Both HA and pectin
300 supplementation increased hepatic uridine and γ -aminobutyric acid (GABA) levels, consistent with
301 altered energy metabolism. In contrast to pectin, HA supplementation was uniquely associated with
302 increased nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide (NAD⁺) and reduced NADH levels, key regulators of β -
303 oxidation, indicating a more oxidative metabolic state in the liver (Figure 2B). HA, but not pectin,
304 significantly reduced hepatic levels of glucose oligomers (maltose, maltotriose, and maltotetraose),
305 which arise during glycogenolysis and reflect dietary starch processing (Figure 2C). Conversely, pectin
306 supplementation significantly reduced hepatic uridine 5'-diphosphate-glucose (UDP-Glc), a precursor
307 of glycogen synthesis, whereas HA had no effect relative to controls. As a result, the ratio between
308 glycogen degradation products and UDP-Glc differed significantly between HA- and pectin-treated
309 mice, indicating distinct impacts on hepatic carbohydrate handling (Figure 2C). HA supplementation
310 also significantly increased hepatic levels of uridine diphosphate N-acetylglucosamine (UDP-GlcNAc)
311 (Figure 2D), a substrate for endogenous HA biosynthesis that plays a role in saccharide metabolism,
312 cellular processes, and O-glycosylation. In addition, HA but not pectin significantly elevated hepatic
313 antioxidant-related metabolites, including glutathione, ergothioneine, and acetylmethionine, suggesting
314 a HA-specific enhancement of hepatic antioxidant capacity (Figure 2E). These results were also
315 supported by direct oxidative stress markers (GSH/GSSG ratio and allantoin) and indirect markers (uric
316 acid, xanthine, and xanthosine), which were reduced after HA supplementation; however, without
317 statistical significance (Figure S9). Further, the GSH/GSSG ratio was increased (Figure S9B).

318 Additionally, pathway analysis of the hepatic metabolome, performed in MetaboAnalyst 6.0
319 (Figure 2F), confirmed significant changes in HA- and pectin-fed mice compared to controls. The most
320 prominently affected pathways included purine and pyrimidine metabolism. Despite this overlap, HA
321 and pectin differed markedly in starch metabolism, nicotinamide metabolism, the tricarboxylic acid
322 cycle (TCA), and purine metabolism. Riboflavin metabolism was specifically supported only following
323 pectin supplementation, whereas vitamin B6 metabolism was specifically enriched following HA
324 supplementation (Figure 2F). Importantly, although pathway analysis suggested involvement of similar
325 metabolic routes, individual metabolites within these pathways were differentially regulated (Figure
326 S5). For example, HA reduced hepatic IMP and uric acid while increasing guanine and guanosine levels,

327 whereas pectin increased inosine and xanthine without affecting uric acid, guanine, and guanosine
328 (Figure S5).

329 Plasma metabolomic profiling revealed trends consistent with hepatic findings, including
330 increased hydroxybutyrate, uridine, and GABA for HA supplementation; however, these changes did
331 not reach statistical significance (Figure S6). Analysis of SI contents showed increased hydroxybutyrate
332 levels following HA supplementation (Figure S7A), mirroring hepatic and plasma trends. Short chain
333 fatty acids (SCFAs) were detected at low concentrations in the SI and colonic contents (Figure S7B,
334 D), with no significant changes. In contrast, HA supplementation significantly increased total SCFA
335 levels in the cecum compared to controls (Figure S7C).

336

337

338 **Figure 2. Impact of HA and pectin supplementation on the metabolome.** A) PCA of the small intestine, liver,
 339 and plasma metabolome. B) Levels of the metabolites associated with energy metabolism in the liver. C) Levels
 340 of the hepatic metabolites connected with glycogen breakdown and synthesis, including uridine diphosphate

341 glucose (UDP-Glc). D) Levels of the uridine diphosphate N-acetylglucosamine (UDP-GlcNAc). E) Differences
342 in the abundances of the antioxidant metabolites in the liver. $N = 10$, $*p < 0.05$, $**p < 0.001$. F) Pathway analysis
343 of hepatic metabolic changes (HA vs. Ctrl, pectin vs. Ctrl, HA vs. pectin) *performed* using MetaboAnalyst 6.0.
344 The y-axis corresponds to $-\log_{10}(p\text{-value})$ as well as colour of the dots (white \rightarrow red = increasing statistical
345 significance), the x-axis and size of the dots correspond to pathway impact, which increases with metabolite
346 interconnection in the pathway and betweenness centrality, which takes into account whether the metabolites act
347 as a bridge between branches of the pathway.

348 **3.3. HA supplementation, but not pectin, alters lipid metabolism**

349 Untargeted lipidomic profiling of plasma and liver was employed to detect systemic alterations in
350 lipid analytes involved in various biological processes. This method detected 482 lipids across 25 lipid
351 classes in plasma and 202 lipids in liver, whereas in liver only phospholipids and free fatty acids were
352 taken into account. The PCA plot revealed a distinct effect of HA and pectin supplementation on both
353 plasma and liver lipidomes (Figure 3A,B). Remarkably, HA-treated samples formed a compact cluster
354 in the liver lipidome (Figure 3B), consistent with clustering observed in the liver metabolome (Figure
355 2A) and SI microbiota (Figure 1A). Volcano plot analysis demonstrated that *p.o.* administered HA
356 significantly modulates plasma lipid metabolism (Figure 3C), whereas pectin supplementation induced
357 only minor and largely non-significant changes (Figure 3D). A similar pattern was observed in the liver
358 lipidome (Figure S8A, S8B). Lipidomic profiles of plasma and liver showed strong concordance,
359 indicating that HA-induced alterations in lipid metabolism extend to the systemic level.

360 HA supplementation increased plasma levels of ether-linked phosphatidylcholines (PC-O) 39:3,
361 39:4, 37:5, and 39:5 as well as phosphatidylcholines (PC) 40:6, 34:2, 36:2,
362 lysophosphatidylethanolamines (LPE) 18:0, and ether-linked phosphatidylethanolamines (PE-O) 42:4,
363 42:5, 38:5, 40:5. Furthermore, HA significantly reduced plasma levels of various
364 lysophosphatidylcholine (LPC) and LPE (see details below), PI 38:5, 36:3, 36:4, PC 32:1, 34:3, 34:1,
365 37:1, CE 16:1, 20:5 (Figure 3C). Pectin supplementation affected only a limited number of lipid species,
366 with a small effect size that barely exceeded statistical significance thresholds (PC 37:2, 35:2, PC-O
367 39:3, and LPC 22:5) (Figure 3D). Owing to the minimal lipidomic impact of pectin, subsequent analyses
368 focus on comparisons between the control and HA-treated groups. At the lipid class level, HA
369 supplementation enhanced plasma phosphatidylethanolamines (PE) and PE-O, reduced LPC and LPE,
370 and did not significantly alter total triglyceride (TG) levels (Figure 3C). These findings were consistent
371 with BIOPAN analysis, which indicated enhanced phospholipid remodelling following HA
372 supplementation (Figure 3G). Specifically, BIOPAN implicated increased activity of membrane-bound
373 O-acyltransferase domain enzymes (MBOAT) enzymes and lysophosphatidylcholine acyltransferases
374 (LPCATs) in both plasma and liver (Figure 3G; Figure S8C), enzymes central to phospholipid
375 remodeling, membrane fluidity, and lipid signaling. Consistent with this remodeling, HA
376 supplementation significantly reduced plasma concentrations of LPC 16:1, 17:1, 18:1, 20:5, and 22:5,

377 as well as LPE 16:1, 18:1, fatty acid 20:5, non-significantly fatty acid 20:4, and 22:6 (Figure 3E).
 378 Similar effects, though less pronounced, were also observed in the liver lipidome (Figure 3F).
 379 Consistent with expectations, plasma concentrations of oxylipins (Figure S9A) and malondialdehyde
 380 (MDA) were low or below the detection limit in healthy mice. MDA levels in the liver remained
 381 unchanged after HA supplementation (Figure S9B).

382

383 **Figure 3. Impact of HA and pectin supplementation on the plasma and liver lipidome.** A) PCA of the plasma
 384 lipidome. B) PCA of the liver lipidome. C) Volcano plots of the ctrl vs HA supplement and D) ctrl vs pectin
 385 supplement in the plasma. All values above the x-axis indicate statistically significant changes. Dots to the right
 386 of the y-axis indicate an increase compared to Ctrl, whereas dots to the left of the y-axis indicate a decrease
 387 compared to Ctrl. The statistical significance threshold is displayed as a dotted line on the y-axis, representing p
 388 < 0.05 , calculated using the Mann-Whitney test. E) Relative levels of the selected plasma lipids. F) Relative levels

389 of the selected lipids in the liver. The E, F y-axis (Fold change) represents the multiple of the average value of the
390 corresponding lipid species/class. G) BIOPAN analysis of lipidomic data for comparison of Ctrl and HA in the
391 plasma. The coloured circle indicates active/suppressed status, and the arrow colour indicates activation (positive
392 z-score) or suppression (negative z-score). The arrow boldening is present if the z-score of a one-tailed test exceeds
393 the 1.645 number – the limit value for the p-value of 0.05. $N=10$, $*p < 0.05$ compared with ctrl (water).

394 **3.4. Correlation of microbiota, metabolome, and lipidome data**

395 To elucidate the relationships between microbiota composition and host metabolic outputs, we
396 performed Spearman's correlation analysis combining SI microbial abundance with differential hepatic
397 metabolites and lipid species. These findings revealed coordinated multi-omics signatures primarily
398 associated with HA supplementation.

399 Comprehensive metabolomic profiles of SI (Figure S10), liver, and plasma (Figure 4A), together
400 with lipidomic profiles of liver and plasma, were correlated against SI microbial taxa. The resulting
401 correlation matrices showed a structured pattern of significant associations between specific microbial
402 taxa and metabolites (Figure 4A), as well as extensive interrelationships among metabolites themselves
403 (Figure S11-S13). Consistent with earlier observations, SI metabolites exhibited fewer correlations than
404 liver or plasma metabolites, reflecting their limited modulation by either supplement (Figure S11-S13).
405 Several HA-responsive lipid species showed significant correlations with microbial taxa enriched in the
406 SI. Increased *Turicibacter* abundance was negatively correlated with plasma LPC 18:1 and LPE 16:1
407 and with LPC 16:1 in both plasma and liver (Figure 4), consistent with prior evidence linking this genus
408 to lipid metabolic pathways. Similar associations were observed for *Bacteroides*, *Intestinimonas*, and
409 *Lachnoclostridium*, which correlated with plasma LPC 18:1, LPC 16:1, and LPE 16:1, while
410 *Bifidobacterium*, *Intestinimonas*, and *Lachnoclostridium* were correlated with hepatic LPC 16:1 (Figure
411 4). Intercorrelations among individual lipid species were also observed, collectively suggesting
412 modulated lipid metabolic pathways following HA supplementation (Figures S11, S12). Significant
413 correlations were observed between N-acetylmethionine and *Lachnoclostridium* and *Turicibacter*,
414 while uridine correlated with *Lachnoclostridium* and *Bifidobacterium*. Interestingly, *Turicibacter*
415 exhibited significant correlations with carbohydrate-related metabolites (UDP-GlcNAc, maltotriose,
416 maltose). *Lachnoclostridium* was also associated with GABA, consistent with their known fermentative
417 metabolic capacities (Figure 4). Although fewer in number, several notable associations emerged from
418 the SI metabolome. *Bacteroides*, *Turicibacter*, and *Intestinimonas* showed strong negative correlations
419 with pyrrolidine, while *Turicibacter* and *Intestinimonas* correlated with long-chain fatty acids FA 22:4
420 and FA 22:6 (Figure S10A,B).

421

422 **Figure 4. Associations between liver and plasma metabolites/lipids and the small-intestinal microbiota. A)**

423 Heatmap based on Spearman's rank correlation (details in 2.7) using hierarchical clustering for bacteria comparing

424 selected lipids and metabolites in plasma and liver. B) Scatter plots of selected lipid or metabolite pairs with

425 bacteria based on their log2 value (Paragraph 2.7) and 95% confidence intervals, r is the correlation coefficient,

426 and the p-value is calculated using Spearman's rank correlation.

427

428 4. DISCUSSION

429 In this study, we compared the effects of two structurally distinct polysaccharides, HA and pectin,
430 on the SI microbiota and associated metabolic profiles in healthy mice using an integrated multi-omics
431 approach. Pectin, a well-characterized and widely used fermentable polysaccharide with established
432 effects on gut microbiota and host metabolism, was selected as a comparator to distinguish HA-specific
433 effects from general polysaccharide-mediated responses. The present work focuses on the SI
434 microbiota, a compartment that remains underexplored, particularly in the context of dietary
435 polysaccharides. Most previous investigations of *p.o.* HA or pectin have primarily examined fecal or
436 colonic microbiota [12,14,19], where both polymers have been shown to induce compositional shifts
437 often interpreted as general dietary fiber effects [3,31]. By contrast, data addressing the impact of these
438 polymers on the SI microbiota composition are scarce. The current study addresses this gap by directly
439 comparing the effects of HA and pectin supplementation on the SI microbiota of healthy mice. To place
440 our findings in context, the differential effects of HA and pectin on the SI microbiota likely reflect
441 differences in substrate accessibility, enzymatic requirements, and the sites of microbial processing.
442 While pectin is a structurally complex polysaccharide predominantly fermented by colonic microbiota
443 [32], HA degradation depends on more specific enzymatic activities that are not universally distributed
444 among gut microbes [33,34]. In addition, HA may undergo partial depolymerization already in the
445 upper GIT, generating intermediate fragments [3]. Consistent with this, the SI microbiota is adapted to
446 rapid utilization of simple substrates and exhibits limited capacity to degrade complex polysaccharides
447 [35,36], suggesting that substrate-specific properties may play a key role in shaping microbial responses
448 in this compartment.

449 Consistent with this framework, microbial degradation of HA is generally considered to occur
450 predominantly in the colon, with more limited activity in the SI. Nevertheless, HA-degrading bacteria
451 have been identified in oral [37] and intestinal niches, and our previous work demonstrated the presence
452 of bacterially-derived HA fragments in the stomach and SI of mice following oral administration [3].
453 Despite this, supplementation with either HA or pectin did not induce detectable alterations in the
454 gastric microbiota in the present study, indicating that the observed microbial effects are localized
455 primarily to the SI. Both HA and pectin supplementation significantly altered the diversity and structure
456 of the SI microbiota, as reflected by changes in alpha and beta diversity metrics. Notably, an increased
457 relative abundance of *Bacteroides* was observed exclusively in the HA-treated group. This finding is
458 consistent with previous reports associating HA with *Bacteroides* expansion in colonic microbiota and
459 likely reflects the capacity of this genus to utilize HA or HA-derived substrates [3,13,38,39]. The
460 absence of a similar response in the pectin group highlights a polymer-specific microbial selection effect
461 rather than a general response to polysaccharide supplementation.

462 Both polymers increased the relative abundance of several genera associated with short-chain fatty
463 acid production, including *Colidextribacter* [40], and a beneficial genus *Bifidobacterium* [41].

464 Additional genera such as *Lachnospirillum*, *Intestinimonas*, and *Turicibacter* were enriched
465 following supplementation with both polymers, with consistently higher levels observed in the HA
466 group. While several of these taxa have previously been linked to dietary fiber metabolism, their
467 enrichment in response to HA in the SI has not been reported and further supports a polymer-dependent
468 restructuring of the microbial community. Although enrichment of putative SCFA-producing bacteria
469 was observed, corresponding increases in SCFA concentrations were detected only in the cecum,
470 whereas SCFA levels in the SI and colon remained largely unchanged (Figure S7B,C,D). This
471 discrepancy suggests that changes in microbial composition do not necessarily translate into
472 proportional metabolite accumulation across all intestinal sites. SCFAs are rapidly absorbed in the
473 intestine and extensively metabolized by enterocytes [42,43]; thus, their luminal concentrations reflect
474 a dynamic balance between production and immediate utilization. The capacity of bacteria to produce
475 SCFA does not necessarily imply that SCFA are actually produced *in situ* under the given conditions.
476 However, some studies reported an increase in SCFA-producing bacteria in response to *p.o.* HA [44],
477 or dietary fiber intake [45,46], however, it does not provide corresponding evidence of a concomitant
478 increase in SCFA levels.

479 An enriched amount of *Turicibacter* is generally considered potentially beneficial, particularly in
480 the context of lipid and bile acid metabolism [47]. In our previous study, which utilized a high-fat diet,
481 *Turicibacter* abundance increased in the cecum and colon, supporting a link between this genus and
482 lipid metabolism. Accordingly, *Turicibacter* enrichment occurred alongside HA-associated lipidomic
483 changes, but whether this reflects microbial contribution, host-driven ecological selection, or a shared
484 response to HA cannot be determined from the present correlation analysis. Several studies have
485 reported correlations between *Turicibacter* and host lipid metabolism, including effects on adipose
486 tissue and dietary lipid handling [47]. These taxon-specific shifts are consistent with the proposed
487 mechanism: HA, due to its distinct enzymatic requirements and potential to generate accessible
488 intermediate fragments, exerts stronger selective pressure on the SI microbiota than pectin. In contrast,
489 pectin is largely resistant to digestion in the SI and is predominantly fermented by the colonic
490 microbiota, where complex CAZyme-driven degradation and microbial cross-feeding occur [48]. This
491 spatial separation likely limits its capacity to drive comparable compositional changes in the SI.

492 Predictive functional analysis by PICRUST suggested that HA supplementation was associated
493 with an increased relative abundance of predicted microbial pathways related to carbohydrate
494 metabolism, including the non-oxidative pentose phosphate pathway and glycogen and starch
495 biosynthesis. These results reflect inferred functional potential based on taxonomic composition rather
496 than direct evidence of microbial activity. Accordingly, the observed patterns may be consistent with
497 an increased representation of genes associated with carbohydrate processing, rather than demonstrating
498 enhanced metabolic activity per se. These inferences should therefore be interpreted with caution. While
499 some metabolites corresponding to predicted pathways, such as maltose, were detected in the SI

500 contents, many predicted changes were not confirmed at the metabolite level, highlighting the
501 limitations of inference-based functional analyses such as PICRUSt. Mao et al. previously performed a
502 PICRUSt-based functional prediction of the gut microbiome following gastric gavage of HA in BALB/c
503 mice; however, their analysis did not reveal changes comparable to those observed in the present study
504 [12]. This discrepancy may reflect differences in experimental design, HA administration route, dosage,
505 or host–microbiome interactions, underscoring the complexity of HA-mediated effects on intestinal
506 microbial metabolism.

507 To investigate the effects of *p.o.* HA or pectin on the metabolome, untargeted metabolomic analyses
508 were performed in the SI, plasma, and the liver, where the most pronounced changes were observed
509 (Figure 2A, S3B). A key finding was the exclusive increase in hydroxybutyrate levels in both liver and
510 SI following HA supplementation (Figure 2B, Figure S7A). This observation aligns with our previous
511 studies showing elevated hydroxybutyrate in UV-induced photoaging treated with *p.o.* HA [9].
512 Although hydroxybutyrate is predominantly synthesized in the liver via β -oxidation, it can also be
513 produced by the microbiota; however, the microbial contribution to circulating hydroxybutyrate levels
514 is proposed to be minimal [49]. Elevated hydroxybutyrate is widely recognized as a marker of enhanced
515 lipolysis and a metabolic shift toward lipid utilization rather than carbohydrate oxidation [50] and also
516 is suggested to exert antioxidant effects by enhancing glutathione activity (Figure 2E) (L. Wang et al.,
517 2021) and by reducing reactive oxygen species formation [52]. Even increased hydroxybutyrate levels
518 have been associated with improving insulin sensitivity, reducing inflammation, and potential
519 neuroprotective effects [53,54].

520 Consistent with this lipid-oriented metabolic shift, both HA and pectin supplementation increased
521 hepatic levels of uridine and GABA (Figures 2B). GABA supplementation has been shown to reduce
522 hepatic TG levels, suppress *de novo* lipogenesis, enhance lipolysis, and improve insulin sensitivity
523 [55,56]. Uridine synthesis is also stimulated by adipose tissue lipolysis [57], linking these observations
524 to the broader lipid-mobilizing phenotype. HA additionally significantly increased hepatic
525 NAD^+/NADH ratio (Figure 2B), key cofactor in β -oxidation and oxidative metabolism [58]. This
526 observation aligns with reports that NAD^+ -dependent sirtuin activity regulates HAS2 expression and
527 can prevent inflammation by inhibiting HA metabolism [59], highlighting a close interplay between
528 cellular energy status and HA metabolism. Remarkably, NAD^+ and NADH are also key components of
529 the Krebs (TCA) cycle, which integrates carbohydrate, lipid, and protein metabolism. That is consistent
530 with our MetaboAnalyst pathway analysis, which identified the Krebs cycle as a key pathway affected
531 specifically by *p.o.* HA (Figure 2F).

532 The preferential utilization of fatty acids over carbohydrates in response to HA supplementation is
533 further supported by reduced levels of maltotriose and maltose (Figure 2C), metabolites generated
534 during glycogen degradation by α -amylase and commonly used as markers of dietary starch digestion.

535 These findings are consistent with previous reports demonstrating increased hepatic glycogen content
536 following administration of as little as 50 mg kg⁻¹ day⁻¹ HA for 15 days [44], indicating that this effect
537 is unlikely to be attributable solely to the relatively high HA dose used in the present short-term study.
538 Moreover, recent evidence suggests that HA can interact with amylase, potentially reducing starch
539 degradability [60]. Supporting this notion, our correlation analysis revealed significant associations
540 between *Turicibacter* abundance and maltose and maltotriose levels; however, these associations should
541 be interpreted as exploratory and do not demonstrate involvement of *Turicibacter* in starch or glycogen
542 metabolism (Figure 4). In contrast to HA, pectin supplementation significantly reduced hepatic UDP-
543 Glc levels (Figure 2C), a precursor of glycogen synthesis. Nevertheless, the ratio between UDP-Glc
544 and glycogen degradation products differed significantly between HA and pectin supplementation,
545 suggesting that HA primarily inhibits glycogen degradation without affecting synthesis, whereas pectin
546 suppresses glycogen synthesis without altering degradation. Moreover, HA increased hepatic UDP-
547 GlcNAc levels (Figure 2D), corroborating our previous findings [9]. Given the central role of UDP-
548 GlcNAc in saccharide metabolism, insulin signaling, O-glycosylation, and HA biosynthesis, this
549 increase may directly reflect enhanced HA metabolic flux [61].

550 The increase of oxidative stress reducing metabolites observed in this study appears to be specific
551 to *p.o.* HA, as evidenced by significant increases in hepatic glutathione, ergothioneine, and
552 acetylmethionine levels, whereas pectin had no comparable effect (Figure 2E). Glutathione is essential
553 for hepatic detoxification, while ergothioneine, a microbiota-derived natural antioxidant known to
554 decline with age [62], and N-acetylmethionine both effectively counteract oxidative stress [63]. These
555 changes correlated with alterations in NAD⁺/NADH ratios (Figure 2B) and were further supported by
556 correlation analysis (Figure 4), consistent with an antioxidant-associated metabolic profile after HA
557 supplementation. As expected in healthy mice, plasma MDA levels were low and remained unchanged
558 following either supplementation. While Huang et al. [44] reported reduced MDA levels in liver and
559 serum following HA administration in healthy mice, and we observed similar effects under
560 inflammatory conditions such as UV-induced photoaging [9]. Finally, amino acids and α -ketoglutarate,
561 which were increased in our previous SKH1 mouse study [9], showed a similar upward trend in the
562 present experiment, although these differences did not reach statistical significance for either HA or
563 pectin (Figure S6).

564 Interestingly, only *p.o.* HA, and not pectin, induced a pronounced shift in plasma and liver lipid
565 metabolism (Figure 3C, D, S8A, B). Whether these metabolic outcomes are indirectly linked to the HA-
566 induced expansion of *Turicibacter*, a genus involved in lipid and bile-acid metabolism [47], remains
567 unclear. Most bile acids were poorly detected and showed no significant changes in SI, liver, or plasma,
568 and correlation analysis did not support a link between *Turicibacter* and hydroxybutyrate, IMP, GABA,
569 or uridine levels. Volcano plots and BIOPAN analysis revealed a reduction in lysophospholipids, an
570 increase in phospholipids, and unchanged TG levels in plasma following HA supplementation (Figure

571 3C, G, S8A, C). BIOPAN further predicted acyltransferases such as MBOAT1 and LPCAT as candidate
572 enzymes associated with these lipidomic changes (Figures 3G and S8C), warranting targeted
573 investigation in future studies. Elevated amounts of PC-O 39:3, 39:4, 37:5, 39:5 and PE-O 42:4, 42:5,
574 38:5, 40:5 following HA supplementation (Figure 3C, S8A) are compatible with lipid profiles
575 previously associated with oxidative stress resistance and immune homeostasis [64], but functional
576 consequences were not directly tested here. HA also increased levels of PC 40:6, 34:2, and 36:2 (Figure
577 3C, S8A), which are known to influence membrane fluidity [65]. In detail, reduced levels of several
578 LPC 18:1, 16:1, 17:1, 22:5, 20:5 were detected following *p.o.* HA (Figure 3E, F). While interpretation
579 in healthy mice remains complex, reductions in LPC 16:1, 17:1, and 19:1 may be relevant to
580 inflammatory lipid-signalling pathways, whereas decreases in LPC 18:1, 20:5, and 22:5 could
581 theoretically promote pro-inflammatory effects [66]. Notably, relative abundances of *Turicibacter*,
582 *Bacteroides*, *Intestinimonas*, and *Lachnoclostridium* correlated with lipids LPC 18:1, LPC 16:1, and
583 LPE 16:1 in Spearman correlation analysis (Figure 4) linking HA-induced microbial shifts in the SI with
584 lipid remodeling. In UV-induced inflammation, *p.o.* HA increased plasma lysophospholipid levels [9].

585 **Limitation**

586 A key limitation of the present study is the relatively high supplementation dose. Administration of
587 2.5 mg ml⁻¹ HA or pectin in drinking water resulted in an estimated intake of ~650 mg kg⁻¹ day⁻¹. This
588 dose was based on our previous work (Šimek et al., 2023), where these concentrations elicited colon
589 microbiome alterations, suggesting that they are sufficient to induce systemic physiological responses
590 and the potential small intestine microbiome changes. The microbiota-modulating effects of HA are
591 dose-dependent, with higher doses required to elicit measurable shifts in microbial composition
592 [3,39,44,67]. Not all measured markers are likely specific to HA and may be related to the relatively
593 high doses used in this current study. Conversely, Huang reported effects of HA on certain metabolic
594 markers at much lower doses (50 and 200 mg kg⁻¹), suggesting that metabolic effects of HA may be
595 unique to this polysaccharide (Huang, et al., 2022). Supplement intake was monitored at the cage level
596 rather than individually, which may have introduced variability in actual intake among animals within
597 the same cage. Although all animals had equal access under standardized conditions, inter-individual
598 differences cannot be excluded. Another limitation of the present study is that only female mice were
599 used to ensure stable group housing and minimize microbiome-related confounding factors, as male
600 mice often exhibit aggression leading to stress, injuries and subsequent separation. Group housing is
601 particularly important in microbiome studies due to cage effects and microbial exchange. Although no
602 signs of hepatic stress were observed, as indicated by unchanged plasma ALT levels, these doses exceed
603 typical human dietary exposures. Future studies should evaluate lower and clinically relevant doses to
604 establish the translational potential of these findings. Although multi-omics integration provides a
605 comprehensive overview, the design remains observational and cannot definitively establish causal
606 relationships between specific microbial taxa, metabolites, and lipidomic changes. Furthermore,

607 PICRUST-based functional predictions should be interpreted with caution due to the inherent limitations
608 of inference-based approaches and incomplete microbial genome representation for SI taxa.
609 Importantly, the present study lacks direct functional validation of microbial activity, and therefore the
610 predicted metabolic functions cannot be confirmed at the level of gene expression or enzymatic activity.
611 Finally, while our correlation analyses revealed consistent associations between microbial genera and
612 host metabolic pathways, mechanistic validation (e.g. lysophospholipids - lysophosphatidic acids
613 interconversion) remains necessary. These limitations highlight the need for future studies employing
614 dose-response designs, gnotobiotic or microbial depletion models, and targeted biochemical assays to
615 define the specific mechanisms through which *p.o.* HA modulates the SI ecosystem and host
616 metabolism.

617 5. CONCLUSION

618 In summary, the results demonstrate that *p.o.* HA acts on the SI microbiome and regulates systemic
619 metabolism. Given that HA is rapidly eliminated from the circulation, its effects are likely mediated
620 within the intestine or adjacent tissues. The SI may therefore play a key role, as it harbours a rich and
621 diverse mucosal immune system. Additionally, *p.o.* HA enhances antioxidant capacity and protects
622 against oxidative stress, unlike pectin. *p.o.* HA influences lipid metabolism (by promoting lipolysis)
623 and carbohydrate metabolism (reduced glycogen breakdown), which could hypothetically induce an
624 overall regulatory shift toward beneficial effects observed in clinical studies, such as improvements in
625 joint function, inflammatory status, skin aging, and metabolic health.

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632 7. CREDIT STATEMENT

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640 8. DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

641 Datasets related to this article can be found at 10.5281/zenodo.18620685, an open-source
642 online data repository hosted at Zenodo.

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